

Forward-Looking to Public-Scholarly Engagement in Baltic Higher Education Institutions

Accelerating the change through institutional and policy change: focus on
Estonia.

Prepared for LibOCS, an ERASMUS+ Project

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List of acronyms

BESPOC - Broad Engagement in Science, Point of Contact

CRIS - Current Research Information System

CS - Citizen Science

DMP - Data Management Plans

EE - Country Code for Estonia

GDPR - General Data Protection Regulation

HEIs - Higher Education Institutions

HSS - Humanities and Social Sciences

KTU - Kaunas University of Technology

LibOCS - This Project Acronym (stands for Libraries for Open and Citizen Science)

LT - Country Code for Lithuania

LU - University of Latvia

LV - Country Code for Latvia

OS - Open Science

PR1, PR2, PR3, PR5, PR6 - Workpackages specific to LibOCS Project

R&D - Research and Development

R&A - Research and Administration

TalTech - Tallinn University of Technology

UT - University of Tartu

VMU - Vytautas Magnus University

IMPORTANT NOTE: throughout this paper, the authors use citizen science and participatory science, which refer to public participation in research projects and initiatives. By using both terms, the authors hope to cover a diverse audience better using either.

Introduction

In a world increasingly driven by the collaborative spirit of citizen (or participatory) science, this forward-looking paper stands as the 30th milestone of the LibOCS project, an example of innovation and partnership funded by the EU's Erasmus+ program. Led by the reputable University of Tartu, this project spotlights the pioneering implementation of the BESPOC model at two of Estonia's premier institutions: Tartu University itself and the Tallinn University of Technology (TalTech). Yet, the ambition of the LibOCS project stretches beyond Estonia's borders, encompassing similar implementations at three other prestige academic establishments in the Baltics / Kaunas University of Technology, University of Latvia, and Vytautas Magnus University.

More than just an example of regional progress, this paper aims to engage the global academic community in a dialogue that transcends geographies. It invites the world to observe, learn, and replicate the successes and lessons drawn from the Baltic experience. The ultimate goal? To foster a rich network of international collaboration and innovation, building together a set of best practices that could elevate the practice of academic public engagement and participatory science across the globe. In doing so, the LibOCS project showcases the potential of concerted effort and shared knowledge, two building blocks for research-related public engagement that are much needed to address the complex challenges of our time related to adopting evidence-based policies and decisions, ultimately increasing trust in research.

Background information on the LibOCS project.

The LibOCS aims to support a future infrastructure that can generate public engagement and lower barriers to participation in research, leveraging the region's existing expertise in open science and increasing collaboration between the LibOCS participating partners. It seeks to bring a remarkable Baltic contribution to the collaborative energy of the public, researchers, and institutions across Europe to tackle complex scientific questions through approaches like CS. Recognising the varying ways of institutional support for citizen science across Europe, the project applies the BESPOC Model (Broad Engagement in Science, Point of Contact) as a central framework for promoting open, shareable research that benefits societal advancement. This initiative is particularly significant in the Baltic countries, where there is a strong foundation in open science but a noted gap in fully leveraging citizen science's potential.

Structured around five objectives, each linked to a specific Project Result (PR), LibOCS aims to¹:

1. Map drivers and barriers of civic engagement in Open Science and share in-depth insights on the role academic libraries can play in Citizen Science activities in the region.
2. Start and maintain a dialogue and action plan among Higher Education teaching/research staff and librarians in the Baltic states, collaborating on a Citizen Science project that involves any volunteer. It will provide an opportunity to focus strategically on the position of libraries in contemporary information societies.
3. Conduct LibOCS training to improve the Citizen Science and Open Science skills of academic and library personnel in the Baltics.

¹ <https://www.libocs.ut.ee/>

4. Create institutional change through testing and implementing a citizen science single point of contact in participating LibOCS universities.
5. Create an Open Access toolkit for librarians on the topic of citizen science with all tools available as open educational resources (OER), open to (re-)use, and repurposing.

The LibOCS project engaged university library staff and academic staff at five Higher Education Institutions: the University of Tartu and Tallinn University of Technology (Estonia), Vytautas Magnus University and Kaunas University of Technology (Lithuania), the University of Latvia, and two private organisations, Web2Learn (Greece), and Immer Besser (Germany).

For a detailed exploration of the project's background, its foundational BESPOC Model, and the initial steps towards its implementation across Baltic universities, we invite you to read the comprehensive 2023 report "BESPOC Implementation at Baltic Universities, A LibOCS Analysis Report and Initial Recommendations," available on the Zenodo platform².

The BESPOC model at a Glance

The BESPOC model, the acronym for "Broad Engagement in Science, Point of Contact," offers a structured framework to develop public engagement and design support services for participatory science within academic and research institutions. First published as a prototype in 2020³ and developed in collaboration between Immer Besser and SKS Knowledge Services in Germany, it aligns with the League of European Research Universities' (LERU) advice for fostering a supportive environment for citizen science projects.

BESPOC comprises 9 modules designed to streamline and enhance the integration of citizen science into academic practices. Since its initial development, the BESPOC model has undergone significant refinement and is now fully prepared for implementation across universities and research-performing organisations. It incorporates a suite of updated guidelines, templates, checklists, and strategic advice designed to facilitate the seamless integration of citizen science into academic practices. Key components of the BESPOC model include:

Policy & Development Plans: Develop and provide ongoing updates to policies specific to citizen science, aiming to institutionalise these practices within academia.

Activities Portal: This is a central hub for transforming policies into actionable projects enhancing project engagement, dissemination, and collaboration.

Partnership Frameworks: Establish collaborative relationships with stakeholders and define the structure, roles, and objectives to boost citizen science's impact.

Templates for Citizen Science Projects: Essential resources and templates to support the ethical and effective execution of projects.

Specific Citizen Science Communication: Strategies for communicating complex research to non-specialists, ensuring transparency, and promoting open science principles.

² Ignat, T., Sabaitytė, G., Laima, B., Lembinen, L., Neerut, L., Kaseorg, S., Rozenberga, G., Birk, K., Tõiste, T., Tautkevičienė, G., Pranckutė, A., & Zourou, K. (2023). BESPOC Implementation at Baltic Universities, A LibOCS Analysis Report and Initial Recommendations (Version V1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10425191>

³ Ignat, T. and Ayrís, P., 2020. Built to last! Embedding open science principles and practice into European universities. Insights: the UKSG journal, 33(1), p.9. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1629/uksg.501>

Research Management & Administration Connector: Integrating citizen science activities with existing research management systems to streamline workflows.

Gateway to Society: Empowering citizens to influence research priorities and ensuring findings inform policymaking.

Legal & Safety Office Connector: Addressing legal and safety compliance issues to protect participants and researchers.

Communities Builder: Cultivating sustainable communities around citizen science projects, fostering personal and collective growth.

With enhanced components, the BESPOC model helps research organisations develop comprehensive tools and strategies to effectively implement a programme of research-related public engagement and participatory science initiatives, building effectiveness for a closer connection between academia and society.

The BESPOC model is a consultancy service offering specialised guidance and support for creating a citizen science point of contact. While its prototype is available in an open-access form, the fully developed BESPOC Model is designed to assist institutions in championing public engagement and participatory science by enhancing collaboration, promoting transparency, and facilitating effective communication in research endeavours. It emphasises the essential roles of cross-departmental cooperation, the backing of staff and infrastructure, and the community's involvement in research activities. This model serves as a comprehensive guide for research organisations aiming to foster a research environment that is more inclusive, collaborative, and has a greater impact.

BESPOC Implementation at Estonian Universities

Our methodology for implementing the BESPOC model was carefully crafted to fit the unique context of each participating university within the LibOCS project framework. Aimed at nurturing a culture of collaboration and comprehensive adoption of research-related public engagement and citizen science practices, this approach included a series of steps: pre-implementation workshops, setting priorities, deploying BESPOC modules, engaging a broad range of stakeholders, and using collaborative digital tools. These steps ensured a tailored and effective integration of the BESPOC model.

The process began with initial workshops and sessions to assess each institution's preparedness and needs for adopting the BESPOC model. Insights from these early interactions were detailed in a LibOCS report (Project Milestone 26) titled "Analysis Report And Initial Recommendations"⁴ marking a key milestone in the project's progression. Following this, universities set their priorities, choosing specific BESPOC modules for early implementation, leading to customised workshops and consultations to address their particular needs.

The project's scope then expanded to include the rest of BESPOC modules, with workshops provided to ensure comprehensive model integration. Recruiting a diverse group of participants, from librarians, researchers to students, was important for assuring a broad perspective on implementation. Digital tools like Google Suite and Zoom facilitated collaboration and communication across teams and locations.

For a deeper insight into our methodology, outcomes, and the specific institutional changes observed, readers are encouraged to consult the LibOCS Report (Project Milestone 29) titled "Citizen Science Institutional Change Through BESPOC Implementations", available on Zenodo⁵. This document provides a detailed account of our implementation, including nuanced execution and evaluation of the BESPOC model across the participating universities.

University of Tartu (UT)

At the University of Tartu (UT), Estonia's oldest and most prestigious academic institution, implementing the BESPOC model has marked a significant step in integrating citizen science more deeply within its structural and operational framework. This process, scheduled between 2023 and 2025, began with foundational steps, including stakeholder consultations and developing a comprehensive citizen science framework. These early efforts were needed in setting the groundwork for the model's adoption, reflecting UT's dedication to enhancing its research and innovation landscape, notably through its Grant Office's support for international collaborations and project funding.

One notable outcome of implementing the BESPOC model has been the strengthened role of UT's library in citizen science activities. This shift elevates the library's position within the university and opens new avenues for academic and societal engagement. Early stages have seen positive impacts, such as increased recognition of the library's role in supporting citizen science, though broader community involvement remains an area for growth. Initiatives like mapping CS projects and developing project templates have laid the foundation for a more structured approach to citizen science at UT.

⁴ Ignat, T., Sabaitytė, G., Laima, B., Lembinen, L., Neerut, L., Kaseorg, S., Rozenberga, G., Birk, K., Tõiste, T., Tautkevičienė, G., Pranckutė, A., & Zourou, K. (2023). BESPOC Implementation at Baltic Universities, A LibOCS Analysis Report and Initial Recommendations (Version V1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10425191>

⁵ Ignat, T., Kaseorg, S., Neerut, L., Lembinen, L., Rozenberga, G., Birk, K., Tõiste, T., Tautkevičienė, G., Pranckutė, A., Zourou, K., & Oikonomou, S. (2024). Citizen Science Institutional Change Through BESPOC Implementations. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10949874>

Despite encountering challenges in stakeholder engagement and resource allocation, UT remains committed to progressing its citizen science initiatives. With a strategic focus on developing supportive tools and events, the university aims to deepen the integration of the BESPOC model within its operations.

For more details about UT's future plans in implementing the BESPOC model, readers are encouraged to consult the LibOCS Report (Project Milestone 29) titled "Citizen Science Institutional Change Through BESPOC Implementations", available on Zenodo⁶, which offers comprehensive insights into the achievements and challenges faced by the five participating institutions.

Tallinn University of Technology (TalTech)

At Tallinn University of Technology (TalTech), Estonia's premier technical education and research institution, integrating the BESPOC model represents a strategic move toward enhancing its innovation and research culture. Established in 1918 and situated in the capital, Tallinn, TalTech is known for its focus on science, engineering, and business, collaborating closely with industry and tech firms to drive technological advancements. The university's commitment to research and development is supported through its Research Administration (R&A) Office and the use of the Estonian Research Portal, ETIS, for managing and disseminating research outputs.

The journey towards fully integrating the BESPOC model at TalTech began in October 2023, with the aim to deeply embed citizen science within the university's library and Research & Administration functions by late 2024. The initial steps focused on creating a dialogue between the library and the R&A office, incorporating citizen science into training programs, and enhancing awareness of the library's resources for citizen science among the academic community. Despite being in the early stages, there's an observable shift in recognising the library as a key player in facilitating citizen science efforts.

Challenges, such as enhancing internal awareness and competency in citizen science among library staff, have been identified, leading to a planned series of internal consultations and targeted training. TalTech is also exploring collaborations with the University of Tartu to share insights and strategies for citizen science integration. With a commitment to advancing citizen science initiatives, TalTech's approach includes strategic planning for future actions and collaborations to strengthen citizen science's role within the institution and beyond.

For a comprehensive understanding of TalTech's implementation process, milestones, and future plans regarding the BESPOC model, interested readers can consult the aforementioned report "Citizen Science Institutional Change Through BESPOC Implementations" (Project Milestone 29), detailing achievements in the five participating institutions.

⁶ Ignat, T., Kaseorg, S., Neerut, L., Lembinen, L., Rozenberga, G., Birk, K., Tõiste, T., Tautkevičienė, G., Pranckutė, A., Zourou, K., & Oikonomou, S. (2024). Citizen Science Institutional Change Through BESPOC Implementations. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10949874>

Recommendations

Here is a set of recommendations that we made in a previous report, “Citizen Science Institutional Change Through BESCPOC Implementations. Report on Achievements in the Five Participating Institutions“. We believe it is relevant to reiterate them in this paper, for broader dissemination.

These recommendations are intended not only to strengthen through citizen science the public engagement of the Baltic universities participating in the LibOCS project. They might be useful for other universities, too. We encourage the readers of this paper to make contact with our project or with its partners to discuss the lessons we learnt and the challenges and solutions we identified.

1. Enhance stakeholder engagement

- Develop targeted communication strategies to engage researchers, administrators, and students better, highlighting citizen science's mutual benefits for academia and society.
- Organise interdisciplinary forums and workshops that bring together stakeholders from within and outside the university to foster collaboration and share best practices in citizen science.
- Steadily build up this kind of engagement. Getting a large variety of stakeholders on board for citizen science or academic public engagement takes time, perseverance, and long-term commitment.

2. Expand public outreach and education

- Increase public awareness and understanding of citizen science through regular public lectures, exhibitions, and media outreach.
- Place citizen science in the larger context of public engagement activities for your organisation and connect your efforts with similar ones from your colleagues responsible for the educational programs
- Offer citizen science (participatory science) training programs for the public to enhance their scientific literacy and skills, making it easier for them to contribute to research projects.
- Actively contribute to transitioning existing communities of interest to communities of knowledge and, further on, to communities of practice and showcase the added value of your university or research organisation.

3. Develop the existing or new digital platforms and systems

- Develop or enhance your existing online portals that facilitate the sharing of research projects and results, allowing for greater transparency, participation, and dissemination of knowledge. While not all your research projects suit citizen science, it is important to responsibly present your ambitions and results to the larger public.
- Explore if your existing CRIS system is suitable for expanding towards a more public interface, including more interoperability with your institutional repository.
- Understand the special requirements for engaging and communicating with the public, including, among other things, the language, the format, and the frequency of your digital communications.
- Utilise social media in a responsible way to engage broader audiences and create communities around specific research topics or projects. Support social media platforms and tools that nurture a healthy audience (e.g. filter disinformation and prevent opinion polarisation).

- Grow your audience in a way that actively supports you in identifying accounts that misleadingly present themselves as being part of (or connected to) your organisation. In return, offer curated and trustful information through your platforms and develop engagement programmes that are openly available for those interested in connecting with research activities.

4. Institutionalize citizen science

- Incorporate citizen science into university curricula by developing courses or modules that cover its principles, methods, and ethics, encouraging future researchers to engage with the public.
- Establish dedicated support structures within universities, such as offices or centres for public engagement and citizen science, to provide guidance, resources, and support to projects involving public participation.
- Aim for streamlining research-related public engagement and participatory science, moving away from strategies that align with the typically short lifespan of projects and embracing long-term strategies.

5. Other recommendations for potential improvements in implementing the BESPOC Model

- Allow your BESPOC service to gain greater adaptability of the BESPOC model to fit your specific needs, cultures, and structures, enabling more tailored approaches to implementing citizen (or participatory) science.
- Adapt your service to modular implementation strategies that allow you to prioritise certain aspects of the BESPOC model based on your immediate goals and capabilities.
- Consider the detailed guidelines and resources for each BESPOC module, including case studies, templates, and best practices, to assist your researchers in the practical aspects of implementation.
- When necessary, consider external training and consultancy services, ensuring that your organisation has access to expert advice and support throughout the implementation process.
- Support the creation of a network among institutions implementing the BESPOC model (or similar) to encourage the exchange of experiences, challenges, and successes.
- Encourage collaborative projects that involve multiple institutions, leveraging each institution's strengths and resources to tackle larger societal challenges through citizen science and research-related public engagement.
- Build professional connections and attract enough resources to develop comprehensive guidelines on legal and ethical issues related to citizen science, such as data privacy, intellectual property, and participant consent, to assist your research communities in navigating these complex areas.

What the Future Could Hold

The commitment to supporting citizen science at the University of Tartu (UT) and Tallinn University of Technology (TalTech), as well as the evolving European landscape for this research approach, suggest a potential for transformative change that could extend beyond their campuses to impact entire Estonia and even the international community. By considering a joint venture, these institutions could envision a future where citizen science becomes integral to university culture and broader societal engagement.

This paper presents a speculative look at what this future might entail under such an ambitious collaboration.

First, advocate for CS's broad acceptance and institutional support. UT and TalTech could lead a paradigm shift in the perception and integration of citizen science at the university level (as different than project-based or department-based levels) through a collective advocacy program. This program could aim to elevate acceptance of Citizen Science by highlighting the benefits and achievements of citizen science projects, thus leading to wider acceptance among academics, policymakers, and funding organisations. This effort might focus on demonstrating the value of engaging the public in scientific endeavours and its impact on creating a more informed society. The advocacy programme should also cement institutional support by demonstrating the need for more resources and a dedicated commitment to building stronger institutional support for citizen science. This might include efforts to secure funding, technological resources, CS classes, and recognition of citizen science efforts in academic assessments. It should also showcase nationwide successful initiatives and projects on participatory science and research-related public engagement, aiming to recruit the attention of researchers and research managers, funders, industry, and the public.

Second, develop upskilling programmes for research-related public engagement and CS activities. Acknowledging the importance of skilled professionals in successful citizen science projects, UT and TalTech could consider programs designed to enhance the competencies of researchers, librarians, and administrative staff. These programs could cover effective methods for engaging the public in scientific research, strategies for communicating complex information to non-specialist audiences, and digital tools to broaden the reach and impact of research.

Third, explore and initiate technological synergy and interoperability. A notable development could be the exploration of interoperability between the universities' Current Research Information Systems (CRIS) or similar platforms and the BESPOC office. This collaboration could enable efficient data exchange and integration of citizen science tools and increase the visibility and management of citizen science activities within academic and public spheres. Another development could be organising the existing institutional repositories in a way that gives plain language access to the university's significant research achievements and all projects that include citizen science.

Fourth, each university could harmonise educational and research-related public engagement activities and resources. Thus, a future strategy might include each university aligning its educational efforts with research-related public engagement to ensure a unified approach to public interaction and—additionally—exploring a synergetic approach with other universities. This alignment could link academic learning with the practical application of research findings. Not less significant, it can support informed public discourse to combat misinformation and promote evidence-based policies and innovations.

Fifth, imagining international engagement and sharing, UT and TalTech could share insights and learnings from their experiences with integrating citizen science into their operations. They should feel encouraged to engage in global dialogues through workshops, conferences, and events to foster a worldwide community of citizen science practitioners.

Sixth, UT and TalTech could organise joint community engagement and training Initiatives. These could include, among others, crafting communication strategies for reciprocal benefits of citizen science (for academia and society), hosting forums and workshops to encourage cross-disciplinary collaboration and exchange of citizen science best practices, developing public training programs to enhance community scientific literacy and participation in research, or promoting the transition from communities of interest to communities of practice, showcasing the universities' contributions to societal progress.

Seventh, a collaborative effort could lead to developing or improving digital resources (e.g., portals) that offer transparent access to research projects and outcomes, encouraging public participation and reflecting the universities' dedication to open science and responsible research communication.

Eighth but not least, explore the potential for joint implementation of some BESPOC Modules. A key focus might be identifying BESPOC modules that could benefit from shared infrastructure, support, and training programmes. This cooperative approach could ensure optimal resource use and enhance the effectiveness of citizen science projects at both institutions.

The Significance of Institutional and Policy Change in Advancing Public-Scholarly Engagement for the Future

It is important to realise the significance of institutional and policy change in advancing public-scholarly engagement. These changes serve as the foundation for transforming the landscape of academia, enabling a more inclusive, collaborative, and impactful interaction between universities and the wider community. Institutional reforms provide the necessary infrastructure, resources, and cultural shifts that empower researchers, educators, and students to actively engage with the public. By establishing frameworks and support systems for public-scholarly engagement, institutions can facilitate a more dynamic exchange of knowledge, foster innovation, and enhance the societal relevance of academic research. This significantly increases the chances of enriching the educational experience for students by connecting academic learning with real-world applications while positioning universities as vital contributors to societal advancement.

On the other hand, a policy change towards stronger public-scholarly engagement plays a critical role in creating an environment that encourages and sustains interactions, leading to more trust in science and, hence, a greater impact on discoveries. Policies that recognise and reward public engagement activities within academic assessments, grant funding criteria, and promotion processes can motivate scholars to prioritise these efforts. Moreover, policies to ensure open access to research findings and promote ethical practices in public engagement help build trust and mutual respect between academics and the public. Such policy transformations are essential for dismantling barriers to public involvement in research, ensuring that the fruits of academic labour are accessible and beneficial to society at large.

It is important to note that a stronger connection between academia and the public should refer to all walks of life, including everyday citizens, policymakers, governmental decision-makers, and the non-governmental side of societies. For example, an academic policy promoting plain language summaries should consider equally an interested citizen working in manufacturing, the members of a related parliamentary commission, or the members of the city council if new research evidence is relevant for such communities.

Combined, institutional and policy changes are strong, ushering in a new era of public-scholarly engagement, where collaboration between academia and society becomes the norm and a publicly appreciated aspect of the academic mission.

A Call for Further Action

The envisioned collaboration between the University of Tartu and Tallinn University of Technology could herald a future in which citizen science is a core element of academic and societal life. Through

advocacy for broader acceptance, commitment to providing necessary resources, and active participation in the global citizen science discourse, these institutions could lead the way toward a more engaged, informed, and cooperative society.

Institutional and policy change represent critical levers for enhancing public-scholarly engagement, laying the foundation for a more inclusive, collaborative, and impactful approach to science and research. Such changes are essential for creating environments where citizen science can thrive, not just as isolated projects but as a core aspect of academic culture and societal advancement. By embedding citizen science within institutional policies and frameworks, universities and research institutions can signal their commitment to democratising science, encouraging wider participation, and fostering a shared purpose between researchers and the public. This shift necessitates a reevaluation of traditional academic metrics, recognition systems, and funding models to support and sustain public engagement in research. It's about reimagining the role of academic institutions in society, transforming them into open platforms for collaborative discovery, learning, and problem-solving.

To all stakeholders involved in the LibOCS project, the journey towards more interconnected academia and society through citizen science is a shared endeavour that requires persistence, innovation, and a collaborative spirit. As we navigate the challenges and celebrate the achievements of integrating citizen science into our institutions, let us renew our commitment to this vital mission. Universities, researchers, librarians, policymakers, and community members are called upon to continue their collaborative efforts, share their successes and learnings, and advocate for the structural changes necessary to embed citizen science deeply within our educational and research ecosystems. Together, we can build a future where scientific inquiry is a collective pursuit enriched by the diverse perspectives and experiences of all members of society. Let's harness the power of citizen science to bridge the gap between academia and the wider world, making science more accessible, relevant, and impactful for everyone.

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